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TOURISM DESTINATION ATTRIBUTES AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Ollor, Helen Y. and Egbuluka, Delight E.

Department of Hospitality Management and

Tourism Faculty of Management Sciences University of Port Harcourt

ORCID Id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1473-0752>

Corresponding author:* Ollor, Helen Y.

Email: hyollor@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

We set out to examine Tourism Destination Attributes, such as: “Amenities, Accessibilities and Activities”, and Economic Development in Rivers State. These were guided by six research questions and six research Hypotheses. A Correlational Survey design was adopted. The sample size of 323 Tourists visiting Centers in Port Harcourt, Rivers State was utilized. Self-constructed instrument tagged, ‘Tourism Destination Attributes and Economic Development Questionnaire (TDAEDQ)’ was used for data collection. The draft of the Questionnaire was validated by our Senior Colleagues in the Department of Hospitality Management and Tourism. The reliability of the instrument was tested using test-retest reliability to determine the internal consistency of the Questionnaire and correlated with Cronbach Alpha. The reliability index was high, which means that the instrument was reliable. The research questions were analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation; while, Pearson Moment Product Correlation was used to test the Null Hypothesis at 0.05 level of significant. The findings revealed mild positive significant relationships between Tourism Destination Attributes, (Amenities, Accessibility and Activities) and Economic Development of Tourist Sites in Rivers State. This indicated that tourism Destination Attributes, such as Amenities, Accessibility and Activities are not very necessary in decision making of tourists seeking where to spend their Leisure time. Hence, it was recommended that the Management of Port Harcourt Tourists Destination Sites should invest more in creating awareness of the happenings at the Port Harcourt Tourists Destination Sites.

KEYWORDS

Destination, Destination Attributes, Accessibilities Amenities, Attractions, Leisure, Economic Development.

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INTRODUCTION

The issue of Destination Attributes and Economic Development has become increasingly important, particularly for countries and regions that rely heavily on Tourism, (Newman, 2015). The Tourism Industry could be considered one of the largest and fastest growing industries in the world, (Ninemeier and Perdue, 2005; Cooper and Hall, 2008). Papatheodorou, (2006) stated that Destination choice has always been an important aspect in Tourism literature and there are various factors influencing travel decisions. Cooper and Hall, (2008) stated that Tourism is subject to collection of influences and factors that determine its relative attraction. The phenomenon of Tourism is one particularly complex. It has, by virtue of its activity, implications in the social, political, cultural and economic areas of activity. The sheer volume and complexity of the offer of Tourist services have led to the development of travel and Tourism Industries. Tourists are subject to certain behavior before, during and after travelling, (Cooper and Hall, 2008). The Tourism potential is determined by the sum of all resources (natural, human, cultural, historical, infrastructure) which, in turn, constitutes to a destinations Tourist offer. This is conceptualized as travel behavior. This behavior is the direct result of interaction between certain personal and environmental variables on a continuous basis, (Cooper and Hall, 2008). Travel behavior can therefore be defined as the way Tourists behave according to their attitudes towards a certain product and their response by making use of the product, (March and Woodside, 2005).

March and Woodside, (2005) state that specific decisions embrace one or more of the behavioral intensions based on the need to behave in a certain way according to highly defined situations. In order to predict travel behavior, it is important to understand how individual characteristics of a person interact with the characteristics of the situation, therefore understanding the positive and negative evaluative factors influencing destination choices of the Tourists, (March and Woodside, 2005).

According to Ibimilua, (2009) some factors have been found to influence the pattern of Tourist patronage of Tourist centers and these factors include, physical appeal the facilities and amenities availability, price, service quality, accessibility and security. For a Tourist Destination to be successful, it is imperative to address Tourist expectation and satisfaction in other to determine the areas of strength to utilize and areas of weaknesses to improve.

Das, (2013) stated that Tourism is the world's largest industry and is growing very quickly. Tourism is becoming a popular leisure activity globally. Millions of people travel from one place to another for Tourism purpose; in search of relaxation, escaping the hustles bustles of their daily life. There is intense competition in Tourism environment globally, and because of the increase in knowledge of the Tourist, Destinations faces competitive threat to be replaced by other destinations, (Pawaskar and Goel, 2014). Therefore, it is essential for the destinations to maintain their competitiveness by understanding the Destination Attributes that informed Tourist choice of a destination patronage, (Palmer, 2000).

Leiper, (2005) defined destination as places where people travel to and choose to stay for a while in order to experience certain features and perceived some attractions. Furthermore, studies by Klenosky, (2002), Reid and Reid, (2003) in their studies on Tourist motivation found that Tourist patronage is dependent on the level of the developments of such regions.

In Nigeria, Destination Attributes has continued to play huge roles in political stability and cultural survival of the people. But the ultimate question involved still remain; would activities have corresponding impacts on the economy?

Destination Attributes such as accommodation, amenities, accessibility, and attitude of the host community, affordability, activities and available package influences Tourist behavior, Bello and Bello, (2020). Tourist preference of destinations has been given much-desired attention in developed countries. Hence, this study will find out the relationship between Destination Attributes and Economic Development in Rivers State.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Nigeria as a destination has been blessed with abundant Tourism Attributes Sites and Events which if properly harnessed will stimulate Economic and Social Development of the country. According to World Travel Organization, (WTO, 2000), Despite the abundance of Destination Attributes, the resources are still ineffective and inefficient. The development of Destination Attributes Areas all over the world contributes to the increase in international Tourist Arrivals. The inability of these potential Tourism countries to tap into the goods that Tourism brings is a major stumbling block to its development.

In Rivers State there are limited destinations capable of positively influencing or attracting Tourist to the state and the manifestation caused by this unavailability of Tourist destinations whereby creating short-changes for State from benefiting from the windfall accompanying Tourist flows.

Jumai, (2017), argued that, Port Harcourt Pleasure Park is among the most visited Destinations in Nigeria. Hence, there is need to find out the relationship between Destination Attributes and Economic Development in Rivers State.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The major Variables of the Study are Destination Attributes (Independent Variable) with its dimensions (Amenities, Accessibility and Activities) and Economic Development (Dependent Variables) with its measures (Income Generation and Employment Generation). The link between the Studies is illustrated in the diagram below:

Fig.1. Conceptual Framework of Destination Attributes and Economic Development in Rivers State
 Source: Conceptualized Desk Research, 2022.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The Purpose of the study is to find out the relationship between Tourism Destination Attributes and Economic Development in Rivers State. Specific objectives include:

1. Determining the relationship between Amenities and Employment Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State
2. Determining the relationship between Amenities and Income Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State
3. Examine the relationship between Accessibility and Employment Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.
4. Examine the relationship between Accessibility and Income Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.
5. Examine the relationship between Activities and Employment Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.
6. Examine the relationship between Activities and Income Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

H₀₁ There is no significant relationship between Amenities and Employment Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

H₀₂ There is no significant relationship between Amenities and Income Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

H₀₃ There is no significant relationship between Accessibility and Employment Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

H₀₄ There is no significant relationship between Accessibility and Income Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

H₀₅ There is no significant relationship between Activities and Employment Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

H₀₆ There is no significant relationship between Activities and Income Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Theoretical Framework

Tourism Destination Attributes

A destination, according to Beirman & David, (2002) is a place of interest where tourists visit for inherent natural or cultural value, historical significance, natural or built beauty offering leisure and amusement. By this definition, any place where these elements exist can be referred to as a Tourist Destination.

Destination Attributes according to Buhalis (2000) are those elements put together to attract and satisfy tourists' intrinsic and extrinsic desires. These elements include: "Destinations Staff Friendliness, Attractions, Scenery, Activities, Amenities, Price, Accommodation etc., capable of influencing tourist satisfaction positively.

Tourism is an important driving force for regional economic development since it contributes to the employment generation of Tourist Sites and enrichment of many related industries (San Martin & Rodriguez del Bosque, 2008).

DIMENSIONS TO DESTINATION ATTRIBUTES

Amenities:

Mason, (2000) and Poerwanto, (2008) stated that Amenities refer to the facilities used to obtain pleasure, for example: Accommodation, Cleanliness and Hospitality (tangible and intangible products). To meet the travel needs of tourists, various facilities would be needed, such as Transportation, Accommodation Facilities, Eating and Drinking Facilities and other Supporting Facilities. These components might not be separated from the infrastructure components, which might guarantee the availability of complete facilities.

Activities:

A destination's "entertainment attribute" can be found in many forms, such as outdoor activities, gambling, and nightlife. Tourists enjoy pursuing entertainment during their trip - even at museums and other cultural sites (Global Insight Inc., 2014). A survey by Richard (2012) reported that 46% of respondents were pursuing for entertainment when they were visiting a cultural site. Entertainment has become an essential attribute of tourist destinations (Formica, 2011). Aalst (2012) argued "in their competition to attract visitors, more and more cities are profiling themselves as an Entertainment City". In the United States of America (USA), entertainment destinations have been growing substantially over the past decade. Branson, Missouri, for example, is an entertainment destination, which has become the second-most popular tourist destination in the USA (Petrick, 2011).

Accessibility:

Accessibility can be defined as the "relative ease or difficulty with which customers can reach the destination of their choice" (Kim, 2008). Tourists' destination choice is often influenced by convenience. Given a choice between similar destinations, a tourist will tend to choose the more convenient one. Thus, destinations, which are more proximate, would be more likely to be accepted over destinations offering similar products that are less proximate (McKercher, 2018). The accessibility of a destination is governed by a wide variety of influences, many of which may depend on much broader economic, social, or political concerns, such as regulation of the airline industry, entry visas and permits, route connections, hubs, landing slots, airport capacities, and competition among carriers (Crouch & Ritchie, 2009). From this point of view, it is difficult to evaluate the accessibility of a destination, based on supply-side. McKercher (2018) suggested that accessibility could be measured by the relative difference in the time, cost, distance, or effort required to access different destinations, based on demand-side.

Economic Development:

Tourism financial flows generated by Inbound Tourism currently generate US\$ 3 billion a day, with the number of international travelers expected to reach 1.6 billion by 2020, (UNWTO, 2011). Tourism Development might frequently be justified by its potential contribution to Economic Development.

MEASURES OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Employment Generation

Tourism, being a service industry, has a significant effect on those areas which have surplus labor. This could be that, for the sector to thrive, skills & efficient human resources would be extremely

important. Human resources have a great effect on local population employment. According to Hall, (2009), there could be positive relationship between the growth of Tourism and increasing employment advantages. Developing a Tourism Attraction as a package could encourage minimizing the extremities of poverty. The author further stated that the employment process could start from the planning of the site, to the actual construction, advertisement & management of infrastructural facilities of the Tourist centers; large number of professional & unprofessional skills, semi-skills and unskilled labor would be empowered with either short- or long-term employments. The proper utilization of these available human resources could be an asset for Tourism Development & side by side further prediction of employment.

Income Generation

Tourism has been lauded as an excellent vehicle for redistributing income from the rich areas with abundant income opportunities to poorer areas where income generating opportunities are scarce, (Spiller and Lake, 2003). For example, one particular form of Domestic Tourism movement that is very popular in Nigeria is the movement of people from the Urban Areas (cities) to the Rural Areas (villages) of Nigeria during the festive seasons, such as; Christmas and Sallah Celebrations. As these relatively affluent urbanized people from places like, Lagos Abuja, Enugu, Port Harcourt, Kano Kaduna, or Owerri, travelled to less populated, poorer but more scenic Rural Areas, it would result to transfer or injection of cash from these individuals who have travelled from Urban Areas to the people in the Rural Areas, (Mowforth and Munt, 2008).

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TOURISM DESTINATION ATTRIBUTES AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Relationship between Amenities and Employment Generation:

According to Mejabi and Abutu, (2010) "Hospitality and Tourism industry could provide a veritable opportunity, with high labor intensive. Hence, it could be a valuable source of employment". This view was also shared by Doswell, (2007) who said that, "Tourism employs a large number of people and could provide a wide range of jobs which could extend from the unskilled to the highly specialized".

It's a service sector which might reduce inflationary tendencies and generate employment opportunities, new investment, new sources of income and governmental revenues and could create earnings through exploitation of the host country's natural and cultural Attributes and promotes environmental protection and care, (Tribe, 2005).

Relationship between Amenities and Income Generation:

Tourism has both positive and negative impact on the national income. Consequently, Tourism firstly brings about redistribution of national income, dividing the world into tourist-generating and tourist-receiving countries, regions and destinations; and, secondly, it has also led to a redistribution of income between sectors and companies within the economy, with the latter reflecting the fact that Tourism consumption differs from personal consumption.

The Tourism multiplier concept is based on the recognition that Tourism introduces extra expenditure into an economy, such as tourists' spending on goods and services in the visited area, tourism-related investment, governmental spending or exports of goods stimulated by Tourism. Tourism Expenditures have Direct, Indirect and Induced Effects. For example, first-round direct tourism expenditures like tourists' spending on hotels, food, beverages, transport, culture, recreation, gambling or shopping is known as direct or Primary Tourism Consumption and equals the amount of Tourism Consumption (Tourism Receipts) in the host country, (Ollor, 2018).

Relationship between Activities and Employment Generation:

Tourism creates valuable employment opportunities. Indeed, commonly regarded as a human-resource intensive activity. Tourism is the world's single largest source of employment, (UNWTO, 2011). Its role contributes to employment and, hence, development varies considerably according to the scale, character, stage of development and relative importance of the tourism industry in a country or destination.

Relationship between Activities and Income Generation:

Tourists could spend their money on so-called Tourism characteristic and other products. The first group could be products created by Tourism industries such as Accommodation, Food and Beverage services, Passenger Transport, Travel Agencies and Tour Operators, Cultural Services and Recreation and Entertainment.

Indeed, it could be Tourism consumption or visitor demand that underpins the economic impacts of Tourism and thus at the center of economic measurements of Tourism.

Tourism consumption represent the total consumption expenditure made by a visitor during his/her trip and stay at the Destination, (WTO, 2010).

Relationship between Accessibility and Income Generation

One of the key elements in the tourist decision making process is the availability of accessibility. If a particular destination or its services are not accessible it only means that such a destination will not even be considered and this is according to the findings of Moore et al. (2012). Accessibility is the ability to locate a destination, reach and get to a particular destination. A study by Yoon and Uysal (2005) argued that tourist destination to enjoy patronage, accessibility is a necessary attribute. This can take the form of transportation such as day or extended tours, aircraft and boats, or infrastructure such as roads, airports and harbor (Hsu et al., 2009)

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used a correlational survey design. According to Nworgu (2006) correlational survey seeks to establish the relationship that exists between two or more variables. Usually, such studies would indicate the direction and magnitude of the relationship between the variables.

Population

The population for this study is the tourists visiting the Tourism centers in Port Harcourt in Rivers State. It is a large and mobile population whose size is unknown. Hence, the population cannot be pre-determined ahead of time.

Sample and Sampling Technique

To determine the sample size for this study, Freund and William (1994) was adopted. The formula is as shown below:

$$n = \frac{(Z_{\alpha/2})^2 PQ}{e^2}$$

Where:

P = Probability for positive response.

Q = Probability for negative response.

e = Tolerable error (0.05).

$Z_{\alpha/2} = 1.96$ from the critical table Z of 0.05 under infinity ∞ .

$\alpha = 0.05$, the significant level

n = Sample size

Applying this formula to the present study, the sample size n is put at 323 which is obtained as follows:

$$n = \frac{(Z_{\alpha/2})^2 PQ}{e^2}$$

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 (0.7)(0.3)}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{(3.8416)(0.7)(0.3)}{(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{0.806746}{0.0025}$$

$$n = 322.69 \approx 323$$

Data Collection Methods

The researchers used both the primary and secondary source of data in carrying out this research work.

The Primary Source was from the Questionnaire; while the Secondary data were from relevant Books, Journals and the Internet.

Instrument for Data Collection

For the purpose of gathering information for this research work, the researcher will use a self-constructed instrument tagged 'Tourism Destination Attributes and Economic Development Questionnaire (TDAEDQ)'. The questionnaire consists of two sections, namely, sections 'A' and 'B'. Section 'A' contains demographic data of the respondents, while part 'B' contains questionnaire variables. Also, in accordance with the five points likert scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (UD) Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted as 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, point respectively.

Operational Measures of the Variables:

A variable is a measurable characteristic of a person, object, place or events. According to Joe (2005), variables are conditions or characteristics that a researcher observes, manipulates, control and measure in order to obtain relevant data that will address his research question and research variables. The two major variables in this study were Tourism Destination Attributes and Economic Development. The Dimensions of Destination Attributes were Amenities, Accessibility, Activities; while Economic Development was measured using, Income Generation and Employment Generation.

Validation of the Instrument:

To ensure the validity of the instrument, the instrument was subjected to face validation. It will be done by the supervisor and other experts in department. These experts will be requested to critically examine the instrument in terms of relevance of the content and clarity of the statement. They will also be requested to advice the researcher on the suitability of the rating scale. Comments from these experts will be taking into consideration in the final modification of the instrument.

Reliability of the Instrument

To measure the reliability of the instrument, the test- retest method was adopted. The first and second test was administered within an interval of two weeks. This exercise was intended to determine the consistency of responses to the questions designed to measure the construct of the study. The first and second data collected was analyzed using Cronbach alpha statistics. The computation gave an 'r' value of 0.71 with the aid of SPSS.

Method of Data Analysis:

Mean score and standard deviation will be used in answering the research questions while Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient for testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Any weighted mean score which is below 3.00 is an indication of a low level of the phenomenon while weighted mean score that is above is an indication of high level of phenomenon under study.

ANALYSIS OF QUESTIONNAIRE

TABLE1: Response Rate of Questionnaire Administered

QUESTIONNAIRE	NUMBEROF QUESTIONNAIRE	PERCENTAGE (%)
Number administered	313	100
Number of Questionnaire returned	283	90.4
Number of Questionnaire not returned	20	7.1
Number of invalid Questionnaire	15	5.3
Number of valid Questionnaire	268	94.7

Source: *Field Survey 2022.*

Table 1 above, shows the summary of the questionnaire administration. As revealed by the Table, a total number of 313 copies of questionnaire were administered to therespondents while 268 copies of the administered questionnaire representing 94.7% were the valid copies of Questionnaire returned.

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

Table 2: Age of the Respondents

	FREQUENC Y	PERCEN T	VALID PERCENT	CUMULATIV E PERCENT
Valid 18-25 years	32	11.8	11.9	11.9

26-35 years	138	50.9	51.5	51.5
36-45 years	56	20.7	20.9	72.4
Above 46 years	42	15.5	15.7	100.0
Total	268	100.0	100.0	

Source:Field Survey (SPSS Output), 2022.

A critical look at Table.2 above, shows the demographic characteristics by age. As revealed in the Table, 2(11.8%) are within 18-25 years, 138(51.5%) are within age group 26-35 years, 56(20.9%) are within age group 36-45 years while 42(15.7%) belong to age group Above 46 years. The age distribution table revealed that the respondents within the age group 26-35 years dominated in the study.

Table 3: Gender of the Respondents

	FREQUENCY	PERCENT	VALID PERCENT	CUMULATIVE PERCENT
Valid Male	115	42.9	42.9	42.9
Valid Female	153	57.1	57.1	100.0
Total	268	100.0	100.0	

Source:Field Survey (SPSS Output), 2022

A critical look at Table 3 above, shows the demographic characteristics by gender. As revealed in the Table, 115(42.9%) are male respondents while the remaining 153(57.1%) are female respondents. This gender distribution Table revealed that the study is dominated by the Female gender.

Table 4: Educational Level of the Respondents

	FREQUENCY	PERCENT	VALID PERCENT	CUMULATIVE PERCENT
Valid NEC/ OND	63	23.2	23.5	23.5
HND/BS.c	121	44.6	45.1	68.7
M.Sc	44	16.2	16.4	85.1
PhD	40	14.8	14.9	100.0
Total	268	100	100	

Source: Field Survey (SPSS Output), 2022.

A critical look at Table 4 above, shows the demographic characteristics by level of Education.

As revealed in the Table, 63(23.5%) of the respondents are NEC/OND holders, 121(45.1%) are BS.c holders, 44(16.4%) of the respondents are M.Sc. holders while 40(14.9%) of the respondents are PhD holders. This revealed that the respondents who had Bachelor Degree certificates dominated the study.

Table 5: Marital Status of the Respondents

	FREQUENCY	PERCENT	VALID PERCENT	CUMULATIVE PERCENT
Single	101	37.7	37.7	37.7
Married	158	59.0	59.0	96.6
Valid Divorced	8	3.0	3.0	99.6
Widow/widower	1	.4	.4	100.0
Total	268	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (SPSS Output), 2022.

A critical look at Table 5 above, shows the demographic characteristics by marital status. As revealed in the Table above, 101(37.7%) of the respondents are single, 158 (59.0%) are married, 8 (3.0%) are divorced while 1(4.0%) of them are divorced. This revealed that majority of the respondents are married.

TEST OF HYPOTHESIS

Decision Rule

If the significant value (P-value) is less than 0.05, reject the Null Hypothesis and accept the alternative Hypothesis at 5% level of significance. On the other hand, if the significant value (P-value) is greater than the 0.05, accept the Null Hypothesis and reject the alternative Hypothesis at 5% level of significance.

H₀₁ There is no significant relationship between Amenities and Employment Generation of Tourism Sites in Rivers State.

TABLE 6: Statistical Analysis for Amenities and Employment Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

Correlations

		Amenities	Employment Generation
Amenities	Pearson Correlation	1	.303**

	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	268	268
	Pearson Correlation	.303**	1
Employment Generation	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	268	268

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 6 above, reveals that there is a mild degree of positive relationship between Amenities and Employment Generation in Economic Development of Tourist Sites in Rivers State. This is because the Pearson Correlation Co-efficient is 0.303; while P-value (2-tailed) is 0.000. Since P-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05, we therefore reject the Null Hypothesis and accept the alternative Hypothesis. This implies that there is significant relationship between Amenities and Employment Generation in Economic Development of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

H0₂ There is no significant relationship between Amenities and Income Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

TABLE 7: Statistical Analysis for Amenities and Income Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

Correlations

		Amenities	Income Generation
Amenities	Pearson Correlation	1	.257**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	268	268
Income Generation	Pearson Correlation	.257**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	268	268

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 7 above, reveals that there is a mild degree of positive relationship between Amenities and Income Generation in Economic Development in Rivers State. This is because the Pearson Correlation Co-efficient is 0.257; while P. value (2-tailed) is 0.000. Since P-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05, we therefore reject the Null Hypothesis and accept the alternative Hypothesis. This implies that there is significant relationship between Amenities and Income Generation in Economic Development of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

H0₃ There is no significant relationship between Accessibility and Employment Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

TABLE 8: Statistical Analysis for Amenities Analysis for Accessibility and Employment Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

Correlations

		Accessibility	Employment Generation
Accessibility	Pearson Correlation	1	.233**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	268	268
Employment Generation	Pearson Correlation	.233**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	268	268

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 8 above, reveals that there is a mild degree of positive relationship between Accessibility and Employment Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State. This is because the Pearson Correlation Coefficient is 0.233; while P-value (2-tailed) is 0.000. Since P-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05, we therefore reject the Null Hypothesis and accept the alternative Hypothesis. This implies that there is significant relationship between Accessibility and Employment Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

H0₄ There is no significant relationship between Accessibility and Income Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

TABLE 9: Statistical Analysis for Accessibility and Income Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

Correlations

		Accessibility	Income Generation
Accessibility	Pearson Correlation	1	.270**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	268	268
Income Generation	Pearson Correlation	.270**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	268	268

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 9 above, reveals that there is a mild degree of positive relationship between Accessibility and Income Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State. This is because the Pearson Correlation Coefficient is 0.270; while P-value (2-tailed) is 0.000. Since P-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05, we therefore reject the Null Hypothesis and accept the alternative Hypothesis. This implies that there is significant relationship between Accessibility and Income Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

H0₅ There is no significant relationship between Activities and Employment Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

TABLE 10: Statistical Analysis for Activities and Employment Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

Correlations

		Activities	Employment Generation
Activities	Pearson Correlation	1	.184**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002
	N	268	268
Employment Generation	Pearson Correlation	.184**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
	N	268	268

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 10 above, reveals that there is a weak degree of positive relationship between Activities and Employment Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State. This is because the Pearson Correlation Coefficient is 0.184; while P-value (2-tailed) is 0.002. Since P-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05, we therefore reject the Null Hypothesis and accept the alternative Hypothesis. This implies that there is significant relationship between Activities and Employment Generation in Economic Development of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

H0₆ There is no significant relationship between Activities and Income Generation in Rivers State.

TABLE 11: Statistical Analysis for Activities and Income Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State.

Correlations

		Activities	Income Generation
Activities	Pearson Correlation	1	.264**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	268	268
Income Generation	Pearson Correlation	.264**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	268	268

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 11 above, reveals that there is a mild degree of positive relationship between Activities and Income Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State. This is because the Pearson Correlation Coefficient is 0.264; while P-value (2-tailed) is 0.000. Since P-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05, we therefore reject the Null Hypothesis and accept the alternative Hypothesis. This implies that there is significant relationship between Activities and Income Generation of Tourist Sites in Economic Development in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This Study sought the relationship between Tourism Destination Attributes and Economic Development of Tourist Sites in Rivers State. To achieve the aim and objectives of the study, we formulated six Hypotheses to guide the study. The Hypotheses were tested using Pearson Moment Product Correlation. The findings are as discussed follows:

The First Hypothesis as stated revealed that there is a mild degree of positive relationship between Amenities and Employment Generation in Economic Development of Tourist Sites in Rivers State. This finding is in line with the view of Doswell, (2007) who said that, Tourism employs a large number of people and could provide a wide range of jobs which could extend from the unskilled to the highly specialized.

The Second Hypothesis as stated revealed that there is a mild degree of positive relationship between Amenities and Income Generation in Economic Development of Tourist Sites in Rivers State. This finding is in line with the views of Ninemeier and Perdue, (2005) which showed that Tourism has been an influence on national economies. The authors demonstrated that, depending on the inward or outward direction of Tourist Flows, Tourism could have both positive and negative impacts on the national income

The Third Hypothesis as stated revealed that there is a mild degree of positive relationship between Accessibility and Employment Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State. This finding is in line with the views of Reid, and Reid, (2003) who argued that, for Tourist Destination to enjoy patronage, accessibility is a necessary attribute.

The Fourth Hypothesis as stated revealed that there is a mild degree of positive relationship between Accessibility and Income Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State. This finding is in line with the views of Crouch & Ritchie, (2009) opined that accessibility of a destination is governed by a wide variety of influences, many of which may depend on much broader economic, social, or political concerns, such as regulation of the airline industry, entry visas and permits, route connections, hubs, landing slots, airport capacities, and competition among carriers.

The Fifth Hypothesis as stated revealed that there is a weak degree of positive relationship Activities and Employment Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State. This finding is in line with the view of Hall (2009) who opined that, there could be positive relationship between the growth of Tourism and increasing employment advantages. Developing a Tourism Attraction as a package could encourage minimizing the extremities of poverty.

The Sixth Hypothesis as stated revealed that there is a mild degree of positive relationship Activities and Income Generation of Tourist Sites in Rivers State. This finding is in line with the view of Doswell, (2007); who said that, Tourism has the capacity to reduce unemployment in any given State or Region if it is properly planned and targeted at improve the lot of the people and not just the host community alone, but the entire Country.

CONCLUSIONS

From the findings of this study, we found lower but positive significant relationships between Tourism Destination Attributes and Economic Development of Tourist Sites in Rivers State. Hence, we concluded that, though Tourist Destination Attributes are necessary in decision making of Tourists when seeking for where to spend leisure times, the level of influence of these attributes on Economic Development of Tourist Sites in Rivers State were of lower extent.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. The managers of the Port Harcourt Tourism should invest more in awareness creation as this will help showcase the attributes at their disposal.
2. The facilities should be upgraded and maintained so as to appeal to visiting Tourists.
3. The host community should be carried along with Tourism Developmental Plans, as no tourist would want to encounter hostile community during visits.

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